

WORK IN AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES RELATIONSHIPS IMPROVE INNOVATION DIRECTIONS INNOVATIVE DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING LABOR RELATIONS IN AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

In the conditions of economic modernization, innovations in the production process the introduction of modern information technologies, and the organization of labor leading to the emergence of new knowledge-intensive sectors of the economy.

"Innovation" of the term modern interpretation famous economist scientist Belongs to Y. Schumpeter (JASchumpeter). In his opinion, innovation is new use of materials and components, introducing new processes, new all new, based on the opening of markets, the introduction of new organizational forms development consisting of new addition and commercialization of combinations of the output function fundamentally exchange.

Here are the conceptual approaches to employment consists of: classic school representatives A. Smith, D. Ricardo, T. Malthus work market A. Marshall, representatives of the neoclassical school, the theoretical founders of the doctrine of J. Mill, A. Pigou work market and price balance based on action to do worker power price while the market coordination theorists is the work with modern theorists of employment L. Brew, KRM McConnell, P. Samuelson work to the market itself special features founders [5, B.115].

From Uzbekistan economists academic KX Abdurahmanov, economy sciences "New Approaches to the Labor Market" by Dr., Professor NK Zokirova Labor market and employment theory, according to his studies becomes concrete in its tasks. This is the development of the labor market and employment laws and trends analysis based on this of fields bottom problems determination and them solution reach ways and methods on the surface scientific preparation of based recommendations, service to improve the efficiency of the labor market who does develop models exit, work based on resource forecasts country and the region economic and social development prospect plans certainties input according to conclusions from preparation consists of [6, B.1].

Economy sciences doctor, professor Sh.R. Kholmominov "Village work of the market formation and development modeling" named research at work the economic content of the rural labor market, its development principles, criteria and indicators scientific and theoretical in terms of studied work in the market worker to the power Demand and offer in

order put econometric models, work in the market sociological studies transfer and them information with provide methodology research done and practical conclusion and recommendations work developed [7, B.18].

Above given to thoughts added without to emphasize must of the population the work employment with, small business and private enterprise, service and service creation of new jobs in the regions due to the rapid development of industries requires innovative approaches to save jobs. But this at work of the population the work with employment and work resources use and them some aspects of the process of strategic orientations have been studied, only Them Uzbekistan village in places of the population the work with provide problems full not illuminated.

Innovative development country international competitiveness factor as assessment of innovative potential and its impact on development based on competition, work release factors for conditions Create, global in competition innovative the role of business increase the first are level tasks.

To achieve this, the development of the innovative policy of the state, its identify mechanisms and levers, stimulate innovation cooperation, socio-economic characteristics of the implementation of the innovative model (micro- (at the macro-, meso level) focus, protection of intellectual property rights and innovative processes control mechanism Create current is considered

Innovation as a key factor in ensuring economic growth, environment and help to create conditions for solving social problems will give. XX of the century in the 1970s economic as a result of the advent of the Internet observation of increasing growth rate, changes in international trade, consumer changes in behavior, emergence of new business models, workplaces opening and in addition to providing employment chance created

Investments in the field of information technology, ensuring growth, unemployment rate its effect on lowering shows. Innovative economy formation creates new forms of entrepreneurship, which is effective to employment effect does.

Innovative economy knowledge based on the economy of the 21st century growth provider main tool is considered Innovative in economics work production and service industries are based on intellectual knowledge and economic to grow provides. Innovative of the economy appear to be innovative entrepreneurship developing in economics venture capital, intellectual property of the right (patent and license) increase, electron of the system organize to be done in business activities cooperative, ie cluster developed method to go provides (Table 1).

Knowledge and information innovative in economics too important factor is considered Development of innovative economy by achieving the following goals done is increased:

1. In business innovations increase.
2. Scientific affairs competitiveness increase
3. International in the market innovative products share increase
4. In economics information communication from technologies (ICT) to use expand.

Innovation creates wealth and jobs in developing countries and is a source of economic growth. At the same time, this news research and technological development (R&D) in developed and developing countries the news different to be managed provides.

Non-technological innovations news and there is of knowledge use, in the market new value to create recorded in official statistics not done [9, B.3].

Of development innovative in type main work release factor has been combining labor with science, technical skill with intellectual skill growth occurs and it determines the economic basis of society. Such "information society", "scientific society" in the description of society in scientific literature "informational economy", "intellectual economy" such as from expressions is used.

Table 1

Traditional economy	Modern economy	Innovative economy
Productivity	Profitability	Innovative news Being
Quantity	Quality	Creativity
Work release to resources dependence	Communicative dependence	Communication, anyway resource development
Long-term business development small change and production in one place operational organize reach	Short term business planning, of changes speed, production operational and strategic organization reach	Permanent to changes business adaptation
Improving the skills of the workforce in the production process done increased	personnel market to the situation and to organizational culture adaptation	Intuition and abilities developme nt
Competitiveness operational cost reduction, tax cuts and laborexpenses reduce at the expense of done is increased	Competitiveness to develop talented employees, business and social infrastructure to develop possibility giving entrepreneurship to develop partnerships and trained employees to provide ideas possibility giver worthy entrepreneurship environment	A developed community transport tools, developed infrastructure environment, person to develop possibility giver fast and cheap web links and cultural environment
Territorial work market	International work market	International work market, virtual business and employment

Innovative to the economy transition changes during [8]

But, to the hand included achievements one with in line some and own the solution waiting serious problems too preserved remains. This is it problems summarizing descriptive if we this Uzbekistan in the economy more extensive traditional production with priority growth, from the existing technical technological system economic to grow intensive factors at the expense of providing modern, modernized technical and technological he slept decision find basically innovative to production is a transition.

Innovative work release model is this national of the economy all from potential efficient use, YIM in the composition ready products contribution increase, economy, competitiveness of the country is to provide.

Innovative production dramatically improves the standard of living of the population is the main way and technical-technological basis. Analysis shows that our economy in the field achieved our achievements at the core big expenses, addition funds spend, of the economy real sector networks and in the fields work manufactured products contain few ready-made products and are mostly natural raw material production and them to export to the eye thrown away.

Innovative method work issued products volume YIM in the composition great less interest organize reach economic efficiency, work productivity low indicators are still relevant. Given above from thoughts come out we mean in the republic being held innovative of politics some aspects time to the soul customization, ie more improvement necessary that we count. Economical from practice known investment, taxes and taxation, customs, finance-credit, directions more improvement and their effectiveness increase refers to the provision of sustainable economic growth in innovative ways legal, organizational and economic basis creates we think.

Also influencing changes in modern labor demand the following factors too there is:

1. Labor and technology between complementarity. Workers It happened to such workers if they were busy with automated work Demand and the work right quantity increases. If workers only machines by execution possible has been tasks performing if their place technique with can be filled. This is due to the introduction of new technology to work has been changes in demand surface brings
2. Providing employment flexibility. If you develop software provided by the publisher to programs has been Demand increases both enough skilled workers until provided in employment significant change does not occur. Software developers and researchers the work right increase increases and stimulates labor supply. However, the elasticity of demand for highly skilled labor is programmatic A large number of employees as a producer of supplies leads to a decrease in wages to bring possible
3. Training of personnel. Created in automation and economics a new type of innovation from technologies usage is high skilled, modern to knowledge increases the demand for available personnel. Workforce skills and technologies between imbalance in labor employment and the work of the right to change slowing down work productivity obstacle to increase does.

In agricultural enterprises work improving relations innovative directions formation economic development and of employment cross-industry movement network to the fields to be entered to investments right has a dependency. In addition, along with investment in various sectors and industries, to regions new technologies, advanced experiences, high qualified specialists come in coming of entrepreneurship fast provides development.

In Uzbekistan, for this purpose, reducing the participation of the state in the economy, private sector fast development through new the work places increase, modernization and diversification of the economy, increasing labor productivity goals and tasks such as ensuring effective employment, high economic growth developed.

In conclusion, it can be said that innovation and new without ideas of the economy present development imagination reached it won't be. Total population in the composition to labor ability age group of weight increased to go or caregiving While there is a tendency to decrease the load, this situation is twofold to the end take coming can:

The first one - to use them effectively to the road not to put as a result unemployment problem relevance occupation arrival;

The second – increased going to labor ability from those of their age efficient significant economic growth can be achieved through its use. It is economically active to increase the share of employed persons in the population, and to increase them in effective work It is necessary to focus on employment and innovative development of the economy in order to work the market manage model and integrated proposed socioeconomic cluster structure from the mechanism use to the goal according to is considered

Therefore, the most important thing is the timely and correct choice of a particular profession personnel training is the basis for achieving high efficiency in production allows you to save the capital spent on, develop the human mind, to express his identity, to fulfill his civic duty, to lead a prosperous life encourages. Such a person public in their work active participation from doing own work he is satisfied with the result, he gets great spiritual encouragement. Most importantly, happy with life being lives

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